

Spacetime with Time Defined Through an Interaction Measuring Space?

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In (1), Prof. Elitzur notes that even though four dimensional spacetime treats ct like a spatial component, there should be an asymmetry between time and space and a distinction between events in the past and present. We suggest that spatial positions must be measured and that this involves an interaction of some sort. We then speculate that time is a label for such a measurement, whether it physically occurs or not. For example, one may move a mass to a position $x=0$ through some interaction and define an initial time associated with this interaction, i.e. t_1 . One may then classically perform one interaction measurement after another to determine this same position $x=0$ (bouncing photons off of the classical object) and each interaction is labeled with a time number. This gives rise to the idea of flowing time. One may note that the interaction does not change the position $x=0$ (classically) and so one may have a fixed x while time continuously changes. This leads to an asymmetry in the idea of space and time, we argue.

Time and Space on the Same Footing in Spacetime?

Spacetime seems to treat time (ct) and space on the same footing. At the same time, there seems to be an arrow of time introduced by an increase in entropy as noted in (1). In (1), Prof. Elitzur argues that there should be further asymmetry in time, i.e. that time seems to flow and that the past and future are not simply like spatial dimensions. We argue that such a sense should appear even without the notion of entropy and the second law of thermodynamics.

Measuring Space

If one has a sense of space (x,y,z) for a particle with rest mass, then the values x,y,z need to be measured, presumably through an interaction which does not change them. This may be done classically for large objects by bouncing light from them. In other words, without any sense of time, one may perform spatial measurements to determine the position x , for example. The question then becomes: What is time and how is it measured? One may suggest the presence of a clock in the room in which the measurements occur, but this clock may be removed.

We suggest that time is a parameter assigned to each interaction measurement or to each potential interaction measurement. In other words, if a particle is at $x=0$, one may continuously bounce light from it to determine its position. One may send in photons one at a time and associated a time parameter to each. In this sense, time flows and is different from spatial variables because it is associated with the measurement of the spatial variables. In other words, $x=0$ may remain constant while time changes (or flows) (due to the interaction measurements). This notion requires no notion of entropy or the second law of thermodynamics.

Lorentz Transformation

We next consider a rest mass, m_0 , at $x=0$, at t . This t is presumably linked to one of the photon measurements of $x=0$. In special relativity, one creates the 4-vector $(x=0, ct)$ and transforms it according to the Lorentz transformation:

$$\begin{cases} x' = g(v) x - vg(v) t \\ t' = g(v) t - vx/c^2 \end{cases} \quad ((1)) \quad \text{where } g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$$

Thus, one has: $x' = g(v) x - vg(v) t$ and $t' = g(v) t - vx/c^2$ ((2))

In other words, x' changes, but so does t' such that $x'/t' = v$, where $-v$ is the velocity of a moving frame which views the particle with rest mass. In other words, in the moving frame, time is again associated with measuring the position of the particle, but since $(x=0, t=0)$ maps to $(x'=0, t'=0)$, t' must find the particle at x' such that $x'/t'=v$. Nevertheless, t is associated with interaction measurements used to find the position x . As a result, time is different from space in that it is used to measure space. Space is not used to measure time because a particle at $x=0$ does not change its value and so a function $f(x=0)$ cannot change its value either.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that even though 4 dimensional spacetime seems to treat ct and x,y,z on the same footing, one may argue that time flows, while x,y,z do not, without using the concept of entropy and the second law of thermodynamics. Specifically, we argue that x,y,z need to be measured and that this requires a measurement (interaction). We associate a time parameter to such a measurement. In principle, classically one could perform such a measurement (by bouncing light from the particle) one after another, hence labeling one new time value after another (flow). As a result, an $x=0$ value may remain constant for all measurements while time (based on each measurement) changes or flows. As a result, time is asymmetric from space because it is used to measure space and not vice versa.

References

1. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pWRAaimQT1E&t=1894s>